

***'Songbirds of the Primate Umwelt: A Zoosemiotic Analysis of Nomascus Gibbons'*, by Baranna Baker & Sofia Bernstein:-**

A Commentary by Amelia Lewis BSc (Hons) MSc MRSB

In this fascinating presentation, Baker and Bernstein make a strong argument for the importance of a biosemiotic approach to ethology and the study of animal communication, via their work on Gibbon vocalizations.

Emphasizing their biosemiotic approach, which relies on empirical data from ethological bioacoustic studies, whilst interpreting the results through a semiotic lens, Baker and Bernstein introduce the behavioural ecology of the Gibbon species they work with. However, they not only give a fascinating insight into the Umwelt of these cognitively complex yet endangered apes, but they also present a theoretical framework by which the study of animal communication, cognition and sociality can be developed to give us better insight into the unique life-worlds of other animal species. Beginning by expanding on John Deely's view that complex semiosis is a unique aspect of human behaviour not shared by any other species, Baker and Bernstein go on to explain why non-humans can, in fact, be viewed as semiotic animals. The presenters rely on empirical examples taken from the many years of study undertaken by Bernstein in their work with both rescued captive, and wild Gibbons, and include a wealth of acoustic and behavioural data to support their arguments. Further, Baker applies semiotic theory to interpret the data, demonstrating the different pathways of semiotic learning, varying in complexity, which are available to non-human species (as well as humans) to enable them to interact dynamically with their Umwelten. In doing so, a testable and valuable model is presented as an alternative to the stimulus-response model currently favoured in traditional biological paradigms.

What is abundantly clear from the wealth of acoustic data presented, is that the title "Songbirds of the Primate Umwelt" is very apt. The spectral structure of Gibbons' vocalizations, and the breadth of an individual's repertoire, are astonishingly complex and varied with respect to the constituent frequencies, the bandwidth, the number of different vocal elements, and the amplitude. Nonetheless, much of the current scientific work on complex animal vocal communication and musicality focuses on birdsong. Studies of avian species, investigating a vocalization's function and context (such as Schmidt et al.'s 2008

work on the function of the nightingale broadband trill), and/or the application of linguistic theory (such as Favaro et al.s' 2020 study on the presence of linguistic laws in penguin vocalizations) indicate that birds as a taxonomic group have received much attention from within the biological sciences. Primates, too, have been the subject of acoustic studies, but, as is discussed in the presentation, the focus tends to be on more familiar species such as chimpanzees, the most famous examples being studies of the 'pant-hoot' vocalization. According to Bernstein, the song of the Gibbon, however, remains relatively unstudied. Moreover, the extent of the semiotic capability of non-human animal species is not generally acknowledged in ethology, to the detriment not only of those species, but also to the scope of human research and knowledge.

A compelling argument is thus made by the presenters to support their hypothesis that non-human animals are aware they are using signs; they are not simply responding to cues in the environment, but have a more complex worldview, with an understanding of their own, as well as others', agency. Along with supporting acoustic spectral data from Gibbon song, examples to underpin this hypothesis include the variation in song structure between the sexes, duetting between monogamous mates and between intergenerational parent-offspring dyads, and the social-learning involved in the ontogeny of song development. The latter is illustrated not only by the description of juveniles learning song from the female parent, but also by the breakdown in song development in those individuals reared in socially isolated environments, such as victims of the pet trade. The evidence presented certainly suggests that members of the Family Hylobatidae are individuals who consciously use signs to interact with both the physical environment and with each other.

This work is therefore invaluable on two counts: firstly, in filling a gap in the primate literature and in aiding Gibbon conservation efforts, and secondly, in shifting perceptions philosophically, with respect theory of mind and cognitive capabilities in non-human species. Whilst current research in biology is beginning to shift toward recognising the complexity and depth of animal vocal communication, the presented work is unique in that it applies semiotic theory, rather than simply searching for a vocalization's compliance with known linguistic laws or identifying function. This approach, for which Deely's work was the foundation, is going to be vital in the study of animal behaviour and communication; if research focusses too intently on fitting animal communication to the laws of human

language, then it is entirely possible we will miss the unique structures of communication found in other species' Umwelten.

The presenters' passion for Gibbons as a taxonomic Family is evident in this presentation, and the desperate need for more research to be undertaken to support Gibbon conservation is made unarguably clear. However, as well as promoting conservation efforts for these socially and cognitively complex, and breathtakingly beautiful animals, this work is going to be vital in re-thinking how we - not just researchers, but the human species as a whole - view and interpret the Umwelten of other species, including recognising that parts of the inter-specific Umwelt may exist, but remain beyond our perception.

I very much look forward to the future publications and studies arising from this work!

With thanks to the presenters for their innovative and informative presentation, and to the organisers for inviting this commentary.

Works cited:

Favaro, L., Gamba, M., Cresta, E., Fumagalli, E., Bandoli, F., Pilenga, C., ... & Reby, D. (2020). Do penguins' vocal sequences conform to linguistic laws?. *Biology letters*, 16(2), 20190589.

Schmidt, R., Kunc, H. P., Amrhein, V., & Naguib, M. (2008). Aggressive responses to broadband trills are related to subsequent pairing success in nightingales. *Behavioral Ecology*, 19(3), 635-641.